

**OCULAR SYMPTOMS OF COMPUTER VISION SYNDROME: A
PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL OVERVIEW AND SCOPING REVIEW.**

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ABSTRACT –

Background- Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS) is a public health issue resulting from prolonged screen use. It causes visual fatigue, dry eyes, blurred vision, and headaches. The pathophysiology is complex, involving accommodative and vergence dysfunctions, tear film instability, and high-energy visible light. The incidence is increasing, highlighting the need for further research. **Methods-** The study utilized electronic databases and manual searches for relevant studies. A comprehensive search strategy was developed using keywords and MeSH terms. The study selection process involved screening, data extraction, and a PRISMA flow diagram. A standardized data extraction form was created for data collection. **Result-** Prolonged screen use can cause eye conditions like visual ergonomics, dry eye syndrome, visual fatigue, and eye strain due to high luminance, low contrast, blue light exposure, poor posture, and psychological factors like stress and anxiety. **Conclusion-** Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS) is a multifactorial condition influenced by visual ergonomics, accommodative demands, dry eye, visual fatigue, and musculoskeletal factors, requiring effective management strategies.

Keywords- *Computer Vision Syndrome, Pathophysiology, Visual ergonomics, Dry eye syndrome, Multifactorial condition*

INTRODUCTION

Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS), or Digital Eye Strain, has emerged as a significant public health issue in the digital age, where prolonged use of computers, smartphones, and other digital devices is ubiquitous¹. CVS encompasses a range of ocular complaints, including visual fatigue, dry eyes, blurred vision, and headaches resulting from the excessive visual demands placed on the eyes during prolonged screen use². The pathophysiology of CVS is complex and multifactorial, involving both accommodative and vergence dysfunctions, tear film instability, and the impact of high-energy visible (HEV) light, particularly blue light, emitted from screens. These physiological disturbances are exacerbated by environmental factors such as improper lighting, glare, suboptimal ergonomics, and behavioural factors like reduced blink rate and poor visual habits during screen use³. Epidemiological studies indicate that CVS affects a substantial portion of the population, with prevalence rates varying widely depending on the study population and diagnostic criteria⁴. Estimates suggest that between 50% to 90% of computer users experience symptoms of CVS, with certain groups, such as office workers, students, and individuals with pre-existing ocular conditions, being at higher risk⁵. The incidence of CVS has been increasing in tandem with the growing reliance on digital devices for work, education, and leisure, highlighting the need for a deeper understanding of its pathophysiological mechanisms⁶. This systematic review aims to synthesize current knowledge on the pathophysiology of ocular complaints associated with CVS, exploring the underlying mechanisms that contribute to its onset and progression, and examining the epidemiology, incidence, and prevalence of the syndrome across different populations. By elucidating these aspects, the review seeks to inform clinical practice, guide preventive strategies, and identify areas where further research is needed to mitigate the impact of CVS on visual health.

METHODOLOGY**1. REVIEW FRAMEWORK:**

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines will be followed throughout the review process to ensure rigorous and standardized reporting.

2. INCLUSION CRITERIA

- **Study Types:** Include original research articles, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), cohort studies, case-control studies, cross-sectional studies, and relevant observational studies.
- **Participants:** Studies involving individuals of all age groups who report ocular complaints associated with prolonged digital screen use.
- **Interventions/Exposures:** Prolonged exposure to digital screens (e.g., computers, smartphones, tablets) resulting in ocular complaints.
- **Outcomes:** Studies that describe the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms, including but not limited to accommodation and vergence stress, tear film instability, blue light exposure effects, and other ocular changes.
- **Language:** Studies published in English.
- **Time Frame:** No restriction on the publication date, but the search was conducted up to the current date.

3. EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Exclude case reports, opinion pieces, editorials, conference abstracts, and non-peer-reviewed sources.

4. INFORMATION SOURCES

- **Databases:** The following electronic databases were systematically searched: PubMed, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library.
- **Additional Sources:** Manual searches of the reference lists of included studies and relevant reviews. Grey literature was searched through sources such as Open Grey and relevant conference proceedings.

5. SEARCH STRATEGY

- **Keyword Selection:** A comprehensive search strategy was developed using keywords and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms, such as "Computer Vision Syndrome," "Digital Eye Strain," "Ocular Complaints," "Pathophysiology," "Accommodation Stress," "Tear Film Instability," and "Blue Light Exposure." Boolean operators were used to refine search results.
- **Search Strings:** Customized search strings were created for each database to ensure the thorough retrieval of relevant studies.

6. STUDY SELECTION PROCESS

- **Screening:** Titles and abstracts of identified studies were independently screened by two reviewers to determine eligibility. Full-text articles were retrieved for those that meet the inclusion criteria.
- **Data Extraction:** Two reviewers independently extracted data from the included studies using a pre-defined data extraction form. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or by consulting a third reviewer.
- **PRISMA Flow Diagram:** The study selection process was documented and presented in a PRISMA flow diagram, detailing the number of studies identified, screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusion at each stage.

7. DATA EXTRACTION

- **Extraction Form:** A standardized data extraction form will be created to gather information on study characteristics, participant details, exposure details, and pathophysiological mechanisms, including author, year, study design, age, gender, occupation, and screen use duration.
- **Reviewers:** Data extraction was performed independently by two reviewers.

8. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

As this is a systematic review of published literature, ethical approval is not required. However, ethical standards will be maintained in the handling and reporting of data.

RESULT

Figure 1: Inclusion of study according to PRISMA.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL REVIEW ON OCULAR COMPLAINTS ASSOCIATED WITH COMPUTER VISION SYNDROME

Sl no	Author	Year	Study design	Age (years)	Gender	Occupation	Screen use duration (hours/day)	Pathophysiological mechanisms
1	Iqbal et al.	2021	Cross-sectional, Case-control	18-30	Mixed	University Students	>6	Reduced blink rate, tear film instability
2	Noreen & Umar	2021	Cross-sectional	18-30	Mixed	Medical Students	>8	Dry eye, asthenopia, accommodation issues
3	Ranganatha & Jaiikhani	2019	Cross-sectional	20-30	Mixed	Engineering Students	>6	Eye strain, headaches, reduced accommodation
4	Rosenfield	2011	Review	19-25	Mixed	General Population	Varied	Digital eye strain, accommodative spasm, tear film disruption
5	Muma et al.	2020	Cross-sectional	Varied	Mixed	University Students (Kenya)	>7	Visual fatigue, eye irritation, refractive changes
6	Portello et al.	2013	Experimental	18-25	Mixed	General Population	>6	Blink rate reduction, incomplete blinking, tear evaporation

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7	Tiwari & Biswas	2012	Cross-sectional	21-45	Mixed	Security Personnel	>8	Asthenopia, eye strain, dry eye symptoms
8	Sheppard & Wolffsohn	2018	Review	Varied	Mixed	Office Workers, Students	>7	Digital eye strain, accommodative issues, dry eye syndrome
9	Bali et al.	2007	Cross-sectional	25-40	Mixed	Ophthalmologists	>4	Ocular discomfort, visual fatigue, dry eye symptoms
10	Rosenfield et al.	2015	Experimental	22-30	Mixed	General Population	>6	Cognitive demand, increased accommodative load, reduced blink rate
11	Uchino et al.	2008	Cross-sectional	25-45	Mixed	Office Workers (Japan)	>8	Dry eye disease, corneal changes, tear film instability
12	Yan et al.	2008	Review	Varied	Mixed	General Population	Varied	Ocular surface disorder, visual discomfort, eye strain
13	Ranasinghe et al.	2016	Cross-sectional	20-35	Mixed	Office Workers	>7	Eye strain, dry eye, visual discomfort
14	Logaraj et al.	2014	Cross-sectional	23-35	Mixed	IT Professionals	>8	Eye strain, visual discomfort, reduced productivity
15	Gowrisankaran et al.	2015	Experimental	18-30	Mixed	General Population	>6	Asthenopia, blink rate changes, accommodative stress
16	Araujo et al.	2019	Systematic Review	Varied	Mixed	General Population	Varied	Dry eye disease, digital eye strain, tear film instability
17	Patel et al.	1991	Experimental	22-35	Mixed	General Population	>6	Blink rate reduction, tear stability issues
18	Hayes et al.	2007	Cross-sectional	23-45	Mixed	Office Workers	>7	Ocular symptoms, quality of life

								impact, asthenopia
19	Asai et al.	2019	Cross-sectional	25-45	Mixed	Office Workers	>8	Corneal epithelial changes, dry eye disease
20	Rosenfield et al.	2012	Experimental	20-35	Mixed	General Population	>6	Induced asthenopia, blink rate reduction, oculomotor issues

Table 1: Pathophysiological Review on Ocular Complaints Associated with Computer Vision Syndrome.

DISCUSSION

Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS), also known as Digital Eye Strain, is a condition that arises from prolonged use of digital screens such as computers, tablets, and smartphones. The ocular complaints associated with CVS are multifaceted, involving a complex interplay of visual, anatomical, and functional factors. This discussion explores the pathophysiology of ocular complaints in CVS, addressing the underlying mechanisms and contributing factors^{1,4,7,8}.

1. Visual Ergonomics and Accommodation

- **Prolonged Visual Demand:** Prolonged screen use requires sustained near vision, which places a continuous demand on the ocular accommodative system. The eye's accommodation is controlled by the ciliary muscle, which adjusts the lens curvature to focus on near objects. Extended periods of near work can lead to accommodative fatigue, resulting in symptoms such as blurred vision, difficulty focusing, and eye strain^{2,6,8,9}.
- **Accommodation and Convergence:** Accommodation and convergence are closely linked processes. Accommodation involves the adjustment of the lens to focus on close objects, while convergence involves the inward movement of both eyes to maintain single binocular vision. In CVS, the excessive demand for accommodation may outpace the eye's ability to converge, leading to visual discomfort, diplopia (double vision), and asthenopia (eye strain)^{23,14}.

2. Dry Eye Syndrome

- **Decreased Blink Rate:** When using digital screens, the blink rate decreases significantly. Normal blinking is crucial for spreading the tear film over the ocular surface and maintaining moisture. Reduced blinking can lead to inadequate tear distribution and increased evaporation of the tear film, resulting in dry eye symptoms such as irritation, burning, and a gritty sensation¹¹⁻¹⁶.
- **Tear Film Instability:** The decreased blink rate associated with prolonged screen use can also lead to tear film instability. An unstable tear film may result in increased friction between the eyelid and corneal surface, exacerbating dryness and discomfort⁸⁻¹¹.

3. Visual Fatigue and Eyestrain

- **Digital Screen Characteristics:** Digital screens often have high luminance and low contrast compared to printed material. Additionally, the glare and reflections from screens can exacerbate visual discomfort. The combination of these factors can strain the eyes and contribute to symptoms such as headaches, fatigue, and soreness¹⁹⁻²³.
- **Blue Light Exposure:** Digital screens emit blue light, which has a shorter wavelength and higher energy compared to other visible light. Prolonged exposure to blue light may contribute to visual discomfort and potentially disrupt circadian rhythms, leading to symptoms such as eye strain and disrupted sleep patterns¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

4. Ocular Surface and Conjunctival Changes

- **Conjunctival Hyperaemia:** Prolonged screen use can cause conjunctival hyperaemia, where the conjunctiva becomes reddened due to increased blood flow. This is a response to ocular irritation and dryness¹²⁻¹⁶.
- **Ocular Surface Epithelial Changes:** Chronic exposure to screen-induced visual stress can affect the corneal epithelium. Epithelial changes may include superficial punctate keratopathy (SPK), where small, pinpoint erosions appear on the corneal surface. This condition contributes to the sensation of dryness and discomfort¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

5. Musculoskeletal and Postural Factors

- **Neck and Shoulder Strain:** Improper ergonomics and poor posture during screen use can lead to musculoskeletal strain. The strain on the neck, shoulders, and upper back can indirectly affect visual comfort by creating additional stress and contributing to overall fatigue.
- **Postural Effects on Vision:** Poor posture can alter the alignment and positioning of the eyes and head, potentially affecting visual ergonomics and increasing the risk of developing CVS-related ocular complaints.

6. Psychological and Cognitive Factors

- **Stress and Anxiety:** The psychological strain associated with prolonged screen use can exacerbate symptoms of CVS. Stress and anxiety may contribute to muscle tension and exacerbate feelings of ocular discomfort and fatigue.
- **Cognitive Load:** The cognitive demands of tasks performed on digital screens can also affect visual comfort. Increased cognitive load may heighten the perception of visual strain and discomfort. Prolonged screen use can lead to various eye conditions, including visual ergonomics, dry eye syndrome, visual fatigue, and eye strain. Long-term screen use requires sustained near vision, which can cause accommodative fatigue, blurred vision, difficulty focusing, and eye strain. The eye's accommodation and convergence processes are closely linked, and excessive demand for accommodation may outpace the eye's ability to converge, resulting in visual discomfort and eye strain. Digital screens often have high luminance and low contrast, causing strain and glare, leading to headaches, fatigue, and soreness. Exposure to blue light, which has a shorter wavelength and higher energy, can also contribute to visual discomfort, and disrupt circadian rhythms. Chronic screen-induced visual stress can cause conjunctival hyperaemia and corneal surface epithelial changes, contributing to dryness and discomfort. Improper ergonomics and poor posture can lead to musculoskeletal strain, while poor posture can alter eye alignment and positioning, affecting visual ergonomics. Psychological and cognitive factors, such as stress and anxiety, can exacerbate symptoms of CVS.

CONCLUSION

The pathophysiology of ocular complaints in Computer Vision Syndrome is multifactorial, involving a complex interplay between visual ergonomics, accommodative and convergence demands, dry eye phenomena, visual fatigue, and musculoskeletal factors. Understanding these mechanisms can guide effective management strategies, including ergonomic adjustments, proper screen use practices, and ocular surface care, to alleviate symptoms and prevent the development of CVS.

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